

ACTION OF NITROGEN TETROXIDE AND ITS THERMAL DISSOCIATION PRODUCTS ON BARIUM PEROXIDE

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Action of nitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products on BaO_2 has been investigated. No nitrite is formed even at 400° . The percentage conversion to nitrate increases with rise in temperature, indicating that the reduction is dependent on temperature.

Action of nitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products on sodium peroxide has been investigated by Addison and Lewis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1874) in which it is shown that only nitrate is formed at all temperatures below 140° , and that a mixture of nitrite and nitrate is formed above 140° . The formation of nitrite is shown to be due to the action of nitric oxide, formed as a result of dissociation of nitrogen dioxide, on sodium peroxide. PbO_2 is supposed to afford $Pb(NO_3)_2$ quantitatively when allowed to react with N_2O_4 (Denstedt and Hasslev, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1907, 38, 133). Action of nitrogen tetroxide or dioxide on any other peroxide does not seem to have been investigated; the action of the former on BaO_2 has been investigated thoroughly in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

BaO_2 was Merck's extra pure quality chemical and was analysed before use. Nitrogen tetroxide was prepared after Oza, Oza and Thaker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2457). The apparatus used for the purpose was also the same as in Oza *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

BaO_2 was allowed to be in contact with the N_2O_4 or NO_2 for one and half hours at 0° and 30° . At other temperatures the heating bath or furnace was maintained around the reaction tube for half an hour only and immediately afterwards the temperature was brought to 30° , and all nitrous fumes were absorbed out in alkali. In none of the experiments any residual gas was removed through the Sprengel pump. Residue at the end of each experiment was carefully weighed and treated with CCl_4 to remove absorbed nitrogen tetroxide, if any, dried with ether and reweighed. In none of the experiments N_2O_4 or NO_2 was found to be absorbed. The residue was then dissolved in water and made up to a known volume through filtration in order to remove insoluble BaO_2 . A known volume of the solution was taken and CO_2 was passed through the solution in order to precipitate barium as $BaCO_3$. The resulting H_2O_2 was destroyed by boiling. Blank experiments were done with mixtures of $Ba(NO_3)_2$ and H_2O_2 in solution to test the stability of the nitrite in presence of peroxide, and it was found that $Ba(NO_3)_2$ was completely stable in a boiling dilute solution of H_2O_2 . The solution was then analysed for nitrate after having ascertained that no nitrite was formed in any experiment. The alkali solution was analysed both for nitrite and nitrate, and within experimental error only N_2O_4 or NO_2 was found to be the product in the gaseous mixture. The results are shown in Table. I

TABLE I

Expt. No.	Temp.	Period of contact.	BaO ₂ taken.	N ₂ O ₄ taken.	Residue formed.	Residue N ₂ O ₄ left.		G. mols of NO ₂ consumed.	
						Ba(NO ₃) ₂ form'd.	BaO ₂ left (calc.).		
1	0°	1½ hrs.	0.110 g.	0.3730 g.	0.1101 g.	...	0.1101 g.	0.3729 g.	...
2	30°	1½	0.100	0.1700	0.1000	...	0.1000	0.1700	...
3	140°	½	0.109	0.2546	0.1090	...	0.1090	0.2547	...
4	170°	½	0.124	0.3070	0.1256	0.00448 g. (0.170 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.1211	0.2994	(0.356 × 10 ⁻⁴)
5	200°	½	0.100	0.3252	0.1031	0.00894 (0.357 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0942	0.32175	(0.706 × 10 ⁻⁴)
6	250°	½	0.110	0.2692	0.1167	0.01341 (0.512 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.1013	0.2643	(1.046 × 10 ⁻⁴)
7	300°	½	0.100	0.1710	0.1170	0.01782 (0.680 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.09854	0.16474	(1.360 × 10 ⁻⁴)
8	350°	½	0.105	0.2000	0.1139	0.03117 (1.19 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0827	0.189	(2.390 × 10 ⁻⁴)
9	400°	½	0.103	0.1960	0.1271	0.0402 (1.530 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0769	0.1816	(3.130 × 10 ⁻⁴)

Gram-molar quantities are shown in parenthesis.

DISCUSSION

No nitrite is formed under the experimental condition even at 400°. The percentage conversion to nitrate increases with the rise in temperature, indicating that the reaction is largely temperature dependent. From the table it can be seen that for every gram molecular quantity of BaO₂ used up, 2 gram molecular quantity of NO₂ is utilised to form one gram molecular quantity of Ba(NO₃)₂, which clearly indicates that the reaction in gaseous system runs according to the following equation.

nitrite forming reaction, *i.e.*

is found to be quite absent under the experimental condition. This is perhaps due to the property of BaO₂.